

AYURVEDIC APPROACH IN THE HEALING OF DUSHTA VRANA**¹Dr. Saumya Nawani, ²Dr. Saurabh Sharma, ³Dr. Manisha Yadav**

¹Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Patanjali Ayurvedic College and Hospital Haridwar.

^{2,3}Associate Professor Department of Shalya Tantra, Patanjali Ayurvedic College and Hospital Haridwar.

Article Received on 16 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 06 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17947797>

Corresponding Author*Dr. Saumya Nawani**

Post Graduate Scholar, Department of
Shalya Tantra, Patanjali Ayurvedic
College and Hospital Haridwar.

How to cite this Article: 1*Dr. Saumya Nawani, 2Dr. Saurabh Sharma, 3Dr. Manisha Yadav. (2025). AYURVEDIC APPROACH IN THE HEALING OF DUSHTA VRANA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 206-212.

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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda Vrana defined as a structural discontinuity of skin and dipper structures. There are two types of vrana *Dushtavrana* and *Sadyavrana*. Wound which defies from stage of healing are classified as *Dushta Vrana*. A wound vice versa of clinical features of Shuddha Vrana. Vrana which does not heal or heals slowly either due to external or internal factors inspite of best efforts of chikitsa-chatushpad called as *Dushta Vrana*. *Dushta Vrana* have cardinal features like foul smell abnormal color with profuse discharge, intense pain with delayed healing. The features of Vrana will be depend on predominant dosha. Acharya Sushruta has mentioned Shashti Upakrama for management of Vrana. *Dushta Vrana* is a long standing ulcer where removing debris enabling drug to reach healthy tissue is more important. So here we can consider it a Non healing Ulcer. Father of Surgery Acharya Sushruta introduced several procedures and drug for Vrana Shodhana

and Vrana Ropana.

KEYWORDS: Duhta Vrana, Non healing Ulcers, Shashti Upakrama, Shodhana, Ropana.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is an ancient Indian medicine system that defines life as a holistic union of body, mind and spirit.

Ayurveda originated in the Indian subcontinent and is considered one of the oldest healing sciences. Shalya Tantra is one of the Important branch of Ayurveda in which surgical and parasurgical techniques has been described for the management of various disease.

Wound is a discontinuity or break in surface epithelium. A wound is a simple when skin is involved. It is complex when it involves underlying nerves, vessels and tendons.

Acharya Sushruta "The father of ancient surgery" mentioned large number of surgical diseases which are affecting the human being in present era. Vrana is one of them which has been managed by human being from starting. Vrana means Splitting or tearing/discontinuity of skin or tissue.

Acharya's have mentioned numerous kwath for Prakshalan of vrana like Panchvalkan, Triphala kwath, Medicated ghrita and oils like Durvadi Ghrita, Jatyadi Ghrita, Jatyadi Taila.

AYURVEDIC REVIEW

ETYMOLOGY OF VRANAS

Vrana is so called by the wise, since it covers (occupies the skin or area of the body) and also because the Vrana Vastu (scar/cicatrix formed later) does not get lost even after healing and remains till the body survives.

LAKSHANA OF DUSTA VRANA

Too narrow, too wide, too hard, too soft, elevated, depressed, too cold, too hot, having one of the colours-black, red, yellow, white etc., frightful, full of foetid pus, muscles, vessels, ligaments etc., discharging foetid pus, moving in oblique track, having deep base, with ugly sight and foul smell, severely painful; associated with heat, suppuration, redness, itching, swelling and boils; excessively discharging vitiated blood and long- standing-these are features of vitiated ulcer. This should be differentiated into six according to predominance of dosha and be treated accordingly.

TYPES OF WOUNDS ACCORDING TO ACHARYA

Types of Wounds according to Acharya Sushruta

Wounds are of two types-intrinsic and exogenous; of these, the intrinsic one is caused by vāta, pitta, rakta and sannipata while the exogenous wound is caused by trauma from human beings, animals, birds, ferocious beasts, reptiles, falling, pressing, striking, fire, caustic, alkali, poison, irritant drugs, pieces (of wood etc.), earthen ware, horn, circular weapons,

arrow, axe, trident, spear etc. weapons. Though, by nature, wound is similar, it is called as of two types because of two types of aetiology and treatment. Lakshana of Dushta Vrana according to different Acharyas.

All types of Doshaj and Agantuj Vranas having lakshans of Dushta Vrana called as Dushta Vrana. All types of Krichyasadhya, Yapya, Duschikitsya and Asadhya Vrana are considered under Dushta Vrana.

Types of Dushta Vrana according to Acharya Charaka

White, with depressed (narrow) passage, very wide passage, much greyish, 'blue, blackish, covered with numerous boils, red, black, very foetid, non-healing and bottle-necked-these are twelve types of defective wounds.

CLASSIFICATION OF ULCER

The types of classification of ulcers are possible

- 1- Clinically
- 2- Pathologically

Clinically an ulcer may be either

- (1) Spreading ulcer- Here edge is inflamed, irregular and oedematous with acute pain. There will be slough and purulent discharge, there will be associated fever, pain and impairment of functions with local tissue.
- (2) Healing-Edges is sloping with healthy granulation of tissues. There will be minimal discharge with absence of slough. Lymph nodes may or may not be enlarged but when enlarged always non-tender.

(3) Non healing - It may be a chronic ulcer depending on the cause of the ulcer, here edge will be depending on the cause- punched out, undermined, rolled out, beaded floor contains unhealthy granulations tissue and slough and /purulent/bloody discharge regional draining lymph nodes may be enlarged but not tender.

(4) Callous- It is callousness towards healing. Word callous means insensitive and cruel and means hard skin. It is also a chronic non healing ulcers having pale, unhealthy, flabby whitish yellow granulation tissue and scanty thin discharge. Ulcer does not show any tendency to heal. Pathologically, the ulcers are classified into three

A. Non specific ulcer

(i) Arterial ulcer

(ii) Neurogenic ulcer

(iii) Venous ulcer

(iv) Cryopathic ulcer

B. Specific ulcers- Seen in tuberculosis, actinomycosis and Melaney's ulcers

C. Malignant ulcers- Carcinomatous, rodent ulcers and melanotic.

On the basis of duration Ulcers are classified into

A. Acute Ulcer- Duration less than 2 weeks.

B. Chronic Ulcer- Duration is more than 2 weeks.

Management Of Dushta Vrana

1. Purvakarm

2. Pradhana Karma

3. Paschat Karma.

Purva Karma [pre operative] includes the preparation of the materials for surgical procedure, and preparation of the patient to make him fit for operation.

Pradhana karma [Operative] includes the eight surgical measures.

Paschat Karma [post operative] includes all the measures for the complete healing of the wound and the wounded areas restores the normal colour and surface without any abnormality.

Acharya Sushruta have mentioned sixty measures of treatment of wound such as-

1. *Apatarpaṇam* 2. *Alepa* 3. *Pariseka* 4. *Abhyanga* 5. *Svedana* 6. *Vimlapana* 7. *Upanaha* 8. *Pacarna* 9. *Visravana* 10. *Sneha* 11. *Vamana* 12. *Virecana* 13. *Chedana* 14. *Bhedana* 15. *Daraṇa* 16. *Lekhana* 17. *Esana* 18. *Aharana* 19. *Vyadhana* 20. *Sravana* 21. *Sīvana* 22. *Sandhana* 23. *Pidana* 24. *Sonitaasthapana* 25. *Nirvapana* 26. *Utkarika* 27. *Kasaya* 28. *Varti* 29. *Kalka* 30. *Sarpīh* 31. *Taila* 32. *Rasakriya* 33. *Avacurnana* (dusting powder) 34. *Vranadhupana* 35. *Utsadana* 36. *Avasadana* 37. *Mrdukarma* 38. *Darunakarma* 39. *Ksarakarma* 40. *Agnikarma* 41. *Krsnakarma* 42. *Pandukarma* 43. *Pratisarana* 44. *Romasanjanana* 45. *Lomapaharana* 46. *Bastikarma* 47. *Uttarabasti* 48. *Bandha* 49. *patradāna* 50. *Krimighna* 51. *Brmhana* 52. *Visaghna* 53. *Sirovirecana* 54. *Nasya* 55. *Kavaladharana* 56. *Dhuma* 57. *Madhu-sarpis* 58. *Yantra* 59. *Aharana* 60. *Raksavidhana*

Principles of ulcer management include following points:

- To determine the etiology
- Accurate assessment of the ulcer,
- To identify and correct morbid factors eg anemia, diabetes, infections, malnutrition
- Drainage and de sloughing of ulcer

Local

- Immobilization
- Elevation of the part
- Avoid repeated trauma
- Regular dressings
- Topical agents-Placentex Gel

Systemic

- Analgesics
- Anti inflammatory
- Supportive treatment e.g. Proper nutrition
- Specific specific treatment for particular dressing
- Antibiotics
- Antidiabetic therapy for Diabetes mellitus
- Hyperbaric Oxygen therapy- HBOT is the use of 100% oxygen at pressures greater than atmospheric pressure. The patient breathes 100% oxygen intermittently while the pressure of the treatment chamber is increased to greater than 1 atmosphere absolute.

Surgical / Parasurgical

- Debridement for slough and granulation
- Radiotherapy for case of malignancy
- Chemotherapy for malignancy
- Leech Therapy

DISCUSSION

Ancient Vaidyas took Vrana Ropana to be serious and crucial concern. Sushruta Samhita have significant numbers of chapters which deals with Vrana Ropana alone. Acharya Sushruta have mentioned 60 procedures called Shadvidha Upkrama which helps to treat Dushta Vrana. Wound healing is a physiological process, but sometimes they are associated with several infections, diabetes mellitus, burns which makes healing slow. Wound healing involves several overlapping events viz inflammation, cell migration, angiogenesis, matrix synthesis, collagen deposition and reepithelialization. It is difficult to develop ideal wound healing as it involves many complex interactions between several cell types, cytokines, adhesion molecules, extracellular matrix proteins. There are variety of chemical substances have been evaluated as wound healing agents, sometimes they are not able to develop healing because these are able to act only at a particular step of healing cascade. It is likely that more effective wound healing agents would be developed from natural products. At present time there are multiple preparation such as Durvadi Ghrita, Jatyadi Ghrita etc.

CONCLUSION

Dushta Vrana is a Kashtasadhya Vyadhi caused by the vitiation of all three Doshas, involving Twak, Rakta, and Mamsa Dhatus. Its chronic nature and poor healing make it a major health concern. While modern medicine continues to research wound healing at the cellular level, such treatments are often inaccessible to the common man due to high costs and limited availability. Moreover, factors like poor hygiene, ignorance, and negligence further complicate management. Prolonged and irregular antibiotic use has led to drug resistance, allergies, systemic side effects such as nausea, and damage to healthy granulation tissue from chemical agents. Hence, there is a growing need for safe, effective, and affordable alternatives, such as herbal formulations.

REFERENCE

1. Manipal Manual of surgery by K Rajgopal Shenoy CBS Publishers and Distributors fourth edition, 2014; 03.
2. Chat A Sushruta Samhita with Ayurveda tatva Sandipika Hindi commentary volume 1 Shana Vedotpatti Adhyaya. Varanasi, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan publisher, 2009; 5.
3. Sushruta Samhita English translation and Dalhan's commentary by Priya Vrat Sharma, Sutrasthan Vranasraav Vigyaneeya Adhyaya Chaukhambha Vishvabharti Oriental Publisher, 2010; 1: 246.
4. Sushruta Samhita English translation and Dalhan's commentary by Priya Vrat Sharma, Chikitsasthan-Dvivrneeyachikitsa Adhyay. Chaukhambha Vishvabharti Oriental Publisher; Reprint, 2013; 2: 245.
5. Charak Samhita English translation by Priya Vrat Sharma, chikitsasthana Dvivraneeyachikitsa Adhyaya Chaukhambha Oriental reprint, 2010; 2: 410.
6. SRB's Manual of Surger by Sriram Bhatt Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers Edition 7.
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